

**A PHONOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SPEECH
ERRORS OF ARABIC – SPEAKING CHILDREN
WITH DOWN SYNDROME IN AL-RAMTHA CITY,
JORDAN**

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SYNDROME IN AL-RAMTHA CITY, JORDAN**

By

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تفويض

نحن الموقعين أدناه، نتعهد بمنح جامعة العلوم والتكنولوجيا الاردنية حرية التصرف في نشر محتوى الرسالة الجامعية، بحيث تعود حقوق الملكية الفكرية لرسالة الماجستير الى الجامعة وفق القوانين والانظمة والتعليمات المتعلقة بالملكية الفكرية وبراءة الاختراع.

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DEDICATION

I dedicate my work to the soul of my father

To my great Mom who never stopped supporting me

To my dearest family and my friends

To my lovely "Ala'a" who encouraged me

To my supervisor, Dr. Abdulaziz Alzoubi for the knowledge, support, and motivation he gave throughout this work, thank you all for everything.

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ABSTRACT

A PHONOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF SPEECH ERRORS OF ARABIC – SPEAKING CHILDREN WITH DOWN SYNDROME IN AL-RAMTHA CITY, JORDAN

By

Hala Ahmad Mofleh Alazizeh

This study investigates the phonological processes of Arabic-speaking children with Down Syndrome (DS) in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. To fulfill the purpose of the study, two groups of children, aged five to ten, were selected. The first group included 15 Arabic-speaking DS children and the second group consisted of 5 normal children. Three methods were used for data collection; PIT Test, Goldman Fristoe Test, and a 5-Minute-Continued-Conversational Speech. Children's speech samples were audio-recorded and transcribed. Speech errors were analyzed according to the DEAP assessment by Dodd et al. (2002). The results revealed the main phonological process errors occurring in the speech of Arabic-Speaking DS children, namely: fronting, backing, stopping, lateralization, coda deletion, onset deletion, initial consonant deletion, final consonant deletion, de-emphasis, de-affrication, stridency deletion, syllable deletion, metathesis, gliding, consonants harmony, cluster reduction, glottal replacement, and nasalization. Also, the results revealed that DS females and males have differences in their speech, males have more errors than females, more difficulties, and more development delays in their speech.

Keywords: Phonological Processes, DS children, Arabic-Speaking children, Errors.

Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Overview

Down Syndrome is a chromosomal disorder caused by an error in cell division that results in the presence of an additional copy of chromosomal 21 (trisomy 21) or additional chromosomal 21 material (Al Shamsi, Talhami and Shaalan 2006). DS children suffer from structural defects in the oral cavity which negatively affect their speech production skills (Miller & Leddy 1998) and highly impact their speech and language development (Al Shamsi, Talhami and Shaalan 2006).

One of the structural defects of the oral cavity of DS children is the presence of a relatively large tongue; the larger size of the tongue restricts its movement when forming sounds especially the alveolar ones (Kumin, 2012). Another defect is the high narrow palate which constrains the tongue's ability to move freely and affects the voice quality (Stoel Gammon, 1997). Other oral structural defects include the shape of the lips and the velopharynx (Miller & Leddy 1998). Functionally, the challenges for acquiring language are increased by these factors, specifically on the level of phonology acquisition (Bernthal et al., 2009). Thus, the language of DS Children develops poorly.

DS Children experience many challenges and difficulties in speech production (Caselli et al., 1988) leading to many phonological errors such as deletion of unstressed syllables, reduction of consonants clusters, substitutions, omissions, and the addition of particular sounds (Dodd, Thompson 2001).

Furthermore, Gammon's (1997) investigation of the phonological development of DS children revealed that DS children moderately gain the phonological arrangement of their mother tongue language. In addition, Van Borsel (1988) conducted a phonological process analysis on the speech of DS children. His findings revealed four common processes; final consonant deletion, fronting, cluster reduction, devoicing of voiced plosives and fricatives. Moreover, Roberts et al. (2005) found other phonological defects such as palatal fronting, fricative simplification, deaffrication, and lateralization of sibilants.

1.2 Problem Statement

The study of phonological processes of DS children contributes to make speech sounds perfectly clear, in order to investigate how to treat children with such disorder. Whilst many previous studies tackled phonology-related topics concerning DS children in English language, to the best of the researcher's knowledge, no study has addressed the phonological processes of Arabic-speaking DS children. Also, few studies have observed the language aspects. Most of the literature on DS adults and children focused mainly on behavioral and social development (Guralnick, Conner & Johnson 2011). For this purpose and due to the lack of research conducted on this topic especially in Jordan, the study's aim is to investigate the phonological speech errors of Arabic-speaking DS children in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. Consequently, it is important to define speech-related phonological processes in Arabic-speaking DS children.

1.3 Significance of the Study

The purpose of this study is to define and explain the phonological processes in DS children in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. This study maybe the first to shed the light on the most frequent phonological processes in the speech of Arabic-speaking DS children. Thus,

this research is a motivation for other researchers to start, to develop, and to improve many contributions in the future.

1.4 Research Objectives

The long-term goal of this research is to reveal the phonological errors in DS children. This goal can be divided into the following objectives:

- To define the phonological processes and errors made by Arabic-speaking DS children in reference to normal children
- To recognize the most frequent phonological errors that occur in the speech of Arabic- speaking DS children.
- To compare the phonological processes of Male and female children with DS.

1.5 Research Questions

The aim of this research is to provide objective answers that are supported by phonological evidence to the following questions:

- What are the main phonological process and errors made by Arabic-speaking DS children in Al-Ramtha City?
- Among the investigated types of phonological errors, which ones do frequently occur in the speech of DS children in Al-Ramtha City?
- What are the differences between male and female DS children in terms of their phonological processes?

Chapter Two: Review of Related Literature

2.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the phonological processes related to the speech of Arabic-Speaking Down Syndrome children, their linguistic development, and the difficulties they might face in the process of acquiring language.

2.2 The Notion of Phonological Processes

The aim of this research is to investigate the most frequent phonological processes in the speech of Arabic-speaking children with Down Syndrome, which will be represented in the subsequent sections: First, we will discuss the concepts of phonological processes in normal children. Second, we will explain the concepts of phonological processes in both normal children and down Syndrome children.

Hodson & Paden (1981:p.191) defined phonological processes“ as deviations from the standard adult speech patterns that may regularly occur across a class of sounds, syllables shapes, or syllable sequence ”.These processes could be observed in children's speech. According to Cohen and Anderson (2011: p.4), phonological processes can be defined as: “descriptions of the predictable, simplified productions typically found in young children’s speech when they are learning to talk“.

2.2.1 Phonological Processes in Normal Children

According to Stampe (1979), Phonological process errors can be defined as mental operations that cause children to substitute a class of sounds or sound sequences

with a more comfortable identical alternative one. Therefore, patterns of errors in sounds in DS children are meant to simplify complex speech sounds or complex words. There are many different patterns of phonological processes (MarizetellhaCeron, 2016); consonants clusters might be reduced to a single consonant like [pane] for ‘plane’.(Ceron,Gubiani,Oliveira&Keske-Soares 2017), [hep] for ‘help’, deleting the weak syllable in a word saying, [nana] for ‘banana’,[mato] for‘tomato’.

Phonological processes can be divided into three main categories: First, syllable structure processes which are defined as a change in sounds that affect the structure of the syllable. For example, a child would reduplicate a syllable, like ‘mommy’ being said as ‘mama’. Second, substitute processes defined as substituting phonemes in children’s speech. For instance, ‘cod’ is pronounced as [tud], and ‘gun’ is pronounced as [dun]. Third, Assimilation processes: a change of sound where some phonemes are changed to become similar to other nearby sounds: it can be either progressive or regressive. For instance, ‘foot’ being said as [tut] and ‘bash’ being said as [bat] (Berman 1977).

In addition, the theory of natural phonology, a modern development of oldest explanatory by Stampe & Donegan (1979), explained the way children apply the phonological processes to speech production. It was suggested that children whose underlying phonological representation include an adult-like form of a given consonant cluster, might reduce this consonant cluster because of limitations in the production of certain sound sequences. For example, /sp/ cluster in ‘spider’ [spaɪdə] could be reduced into [paɪdə] and /pl/ cluster in plane [pleɪn] could be reduced into [peɪn] (Grunwell, 1987& Ingram,1976). Furthermore, Perumal, Raghunathan, Boominathan, andSreedevi(2017) investigated the occurrence of phonological processes in the speech of Tamil-speaking children. The results showed that levels of phonological processes decline as age increases,

except for stopping of liquids and cluster reduction which persisted beyond the age of three.

2.2.2 Phonological Processes in children with Down Syndrome

According to Edition & Bauman-Waengler (2012), phonological processes in Down Syndrome individuals were classified as developmental or non-developmental. Developmental phonological processes indicate final consonant deletion like 'drink' realized as [drin?], stopping cluster reduction like 'jump' realized as [jup], fronting like [tootie] for 'cookie' and gliding like [yeyo] for 'yellow'. On the other hand, non-developmental processes represent processes such as glottal replacement [ʔip.] for 'lip', initial consonant deletion such as [unny] for 'bunny', fricatives like [ve] for 'we' and affricatives [joor] for 'door.'

Stoel – Gammon (2001) described the phonological development in DS children and summarized several factors that influence phonological acquisition including; hearing loss, anatomical, and physical differences. Furthermore, four aspects of phonology in Down Syndrome children were described: First, the pre-linguistics stage; this stage investigates the pre-speech development of the Down Syndrome children. Second, the speech transition stage which is highly similar to that with typically developing children. Third, the word production stage which is identical to that of typically developing children. Stops, nasals, and glide consonants are produced correctly, while fricatives, affricates, and liquids are sometimes produced with errors. The Fourth stage is speech intelligibility explained as follows: "At age four, the speech of children would be fully intelligible, while their phonological development wouldn't be completed" Caplon & Gleason (1988). Gammon (2001) found that DS children moderately gain the phonological arrangement of their mother tongue language. In general, all languages represent universal properties of phonological processes.

This study investigates both developmental and non-developmental phonological processes in Arabic-speaking DS children in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. This research focuses on consonant clusters produced as singleton consonants, deletion of final consonants, affricatives and fricatives produced as stops, word-initial liquids produced as glides, and other processes.

2.3 Phonological Disorders

This section discusses the notion of and reasons for the phonological disorders in DS children.

2.3.1 The Notion of Phonological Disorder

Phonological disorder (PD) is a type of disorder in speech production; children do not produce some or all of the speech sounds expected for their age group. Ferguson, Menn & Gammon (1992) defined phonological disorders as factors that influence on the speaker's production and speaker's mental of speech sounds. In addition, Gammon & Dunn (1985) described phonological disorder as failing to express discourse sounds. In other words, it is a fault in the way in which sounds are stored and used in the mental lexicon.

According to Williamson (2014), phonological disorders are phonemic in nature, while articulation disorders are phonetic. Moreover, children with phonological disorder may pronounce all the sounds without any difficulties; however, they might face problems associated with the physical articulation, especially, when they produce the speech sounds in context.

In addition, Bird and Bishop (1992) rejected the idea that phonological disorders can only be attributed to underlying hearing problems, as PD children show some ability to discriminate sound contrasts that are absent in their own pronunciation repertoire. Many

children with PD show phonological processes that are identical to those produced by younger children (Lenonard, 1973).

2.3.2 Phonological Disorder in Children

This section includes previous studies related to phonological disorders in children.

According to (Hamilton 1993), all children show some ability to differentiate contrasts they could not produce. PD children cannot analyze words at the phoneme level due to significant deficits in their ability to recognize phoneme constancy in any word contexts. Moreover, phonological disorders may affect motor skills or speech sound production in children(Cermak, Ward& Ward, 1986). Children with phonological disorders might fail to produce vowels (Clement &Wijnen, 1994). Furthermore, Iacono &Dodd (1989) explained that articulating speech in preschool years is often associated with non-developmental phonological processes like initial consonant deletion.

In addition, Iacono&Dodd (1989) investigated the phonological changes during remediation for PD children revealed that the majority of children made quantitative improvements in terms of consonants produced correctly. Fox and Rogers (2002) pointed out that the performance of PD children's speech was poorer than their normal peers.

2.4 Down Syndrome

This section discusses the definition of Down Syndrome, structural variations in the motor oral cavity, and cognitive skills. The subsequent sections will discuss oral–motor skills and cognitive skills.

2.4.1 The Notion of Down Syndrome

Down Syndrome (DS) is defined as a chromosomal disorder caused by an error in cell division that results in the presence of an additional copy of chromosome 21 (trisomy 21) or additional chromosomal 21 material (Al Shamsi, Talhami and Shaalan, 2006). It occurs in all ethnic and economic varieties. It is the most popular chromosomal cause of mild to moderate mental disability. However, the communication skills of DS individuals are greatly influenced by other aspects, such as hearing, oral-motor, cognitive, social, and paralinguistic defects. (Al Shamsi, Talhami, and Shaalan, 2006).

2.4.2 Oral – Motor Structure Characteristics

DS Children's special physical characteristics affect speech production and development (Malkin, Roberts, Price 2007). According to Stoel-Gammon (1997) and (Miller & Leddy, 1998) there are many structural differences in down syndrome include a small oral cavity, large tongue and a narrow high arched palate, missing or additional muscles characterize facial structures. In addition, they have a wide nasal root, a narrow soft nose, high nasal tip, a high upper lip, and short and narrow palate (Bourdiol, Veyrune, Faulks, Hennequin 1999).

Moreover, children with DS have a high narrow palate which may constrain the tongue's ability to move freely. Functionally, all these factors provide challenges for acquiring language, specifically, on the level of phonology acquisition (Bernthal et al., 2009). According to Schott & Holfelder's study (2005) which examined motor skills and executive control skills in DS children from ages 6 to 17, DS children develop slowly. Accordingly, it is noticed that they show some delay in acquiring skills like standing, walking, controlling their attention and responses.

2.4.3 Cognitive Characteristics

DS Children show delays in cognitive domains such as communication, memory, and task performance, limited cognitive skills; concentrating, analyzing concepts, and remembering (McDuffie and Abbeduto,2009).

The expressive language skills are much weaker than the receptive skills in DS children (Caselli,Vicari,Longobardi,Lami,Pizzoli & Stella,1998) as in: the deletion of unstressed syllables, errors in final syllable sounds, reduction of consonant clusters, substitutions, omissions, and additions of particular sounds (Dodd & Thompson, 2001).In their pre- and school-age years, phonological errors in DS children are common features and often continue to appear in adulthood. Laws and Bishop (2003) investigated the expressive and receptive language skills in DS children. They found that the vocabulary performance of DS children is similar to typically developing children.

In general, DS children's ability to acquire language in the grammatical and pronunciation domain is impaired (Bray &Woolnough1988). For instance, from a grammatical point of view, DS children tend to utilize keywords, such as ‘went swimming Dad’ rather than ‘I went swimming last night with my dad’.

Furthermore, a study by Broadley, Laws, MacDonald, and Buckley (1995) assessed the performance of 30 boys and 32 girls with DS in working memory tasks (auditory task & visual task). Their findings showed that DS children possess a poor auditory memory or recognition memory. Dodd and Crosbie (2005) concluded that DS children’s visual memory is stronger than their auditory memory (verbal input). For instance, DS children find that remembering the steps on how to play a game is simpler than following the instructions of that game(Fidler & Nadel, 2007).

Penke (2018) investigated whether finite verbal morphology is affected in DS children/adolescents. The study revealed that a significant number of DS children are challenged in marking verbal agreement and fail to achieve an acquisition criterion. Nevertheless, when consonants do not convey verbal agreement, the development of word-final consonants succeeds.

2.5 Phonological processes in Children with DS

This section discusses the phonological processes in DS children. It describes the factors that influence phonological development and speech production in DS children, in addition this section explores the differences in the development of phonological processes in typical and DS children.

For many years, Phonology has been the focus of numerous studies of DS individuals. In an earlier study by Stoel-Gammon (1980) four DS children participated, results concluded that although kids pronounced nearly all the phonemes, their ability to pronounce them correctly was restricted to their positions in the word, also it indicated the similarity in phonological processes between normal children and DS children, and phonological skills of DS children were way better than other language skills.

Stoel- Gammon (2001) discussed and described the factors that influence phonological development in DS children. He pointed out to four stages: starting with the pre-linguistic stage, the transition to speech, phonology of single words, and phonological characteristics of conversational speech.

As stated by Bleile& Schwarz (1984), stops, nasals, and glide consonants tend to be delivered precisely, while affricates, fricatives, and liquids sometimes inaccurate. Consonant clusters produced by children with DS are singleton consonants, word-final

consonants are omitted, fricatives and affricates are produced as stops, word-initial liquids are produced as glides.

Phonological process analysis has highlighted the similarities between DS children and typically developing children with several frequently occurring patterns such as producing consonant clusters as singleton consonants, omitting word-final consonants, producing target fricatives and affricates as stops, and producing word-initial liquids as glides (Cholmain, 1994; and Van Borsel, 1996). In addition, Dodd & Leahy (1989) found that DS children and normal children have the same characteristics of word production.

Parsons and Iacono (1992) emphasized that the articulation of DS children has more similarities than variations to the normal children articulation. A more recent study done by Yousif (2018) has come to the same conclusion after examining the phonological skills of 17 British English-speaking DS children and 20 typical children.

"Phonological Abilities of Individuals with Down Syndrome" investigates whether DS individuals possess a unique form of speech that differs from ordinary individuals, Carl Parsons & Teresa Iacono (1992) utilized effective methods to analyze and thoroughly examine the speech of a group of DS individuals. Hence, a full investigation of the phonology of the chosen sample was conducted, including the presence of consonant phonemes, phonological processes, and processes-related errors. Three methods for data collection were used: Goldman-Fristoe Test of Articulation, the Parsons-Iacono Test (PIT), and a 5-minute-continued-conversational speech. Both the Goldman-Fristoe Test and the PIT were concerned with naming 35 pictures and 105 pictures, respectively. The PIT was used to extract the words that represent variant syllable types in the speech of DS individuals (i.e., CVC, CV, two syllables, and multi syllables). The data were audio-recorded, transcribed, and then randomly re-transcribed by a second researcher to ensure reliability.

According to Parsons and Iacono (1992), the three most frequently occurring phonological processes produced by DS individuals with the highest RIU values are cluster reduction, final consonant deletion, and fronting fricatives .

Gammon (1997) provided an overview of the literature on phonological development and highlighted the differences between developmental phonology of DS children and typically developing children: the phonological acquisition of DS children, hearing status, the nature of linguistics input received, and the structure of the oral cavity of children with DS that differs from typically developing children.

Stoel-Gammon (1997; 2001) summarized the phonological processes in DS children as follows: (a) consonant clusters produced as singleton consonants (cluster reduction); (b) word-final consonants deleted (final consonant deletion); (c) target fricatives produced as stops (stopping); (d) aspirated voiceless stops in the initial position (pre-vocalic voicing); (e) word-initial liquids produced as glides (gliding); (f) word-final liquids produced as vowels (vocalization); and (g) word-final obstruent devoiced (final consonant devoicing).

A study by Van Borsel (1988) reported that there are four common phonological processes among DS children; cluster reduction, deletion of final consonants, fronting of palatals, and devoicing of voiced plosives and fricatives. Other processes appeared to be frequent but not common, such as liquid deviation, backing of /t/ and /d/, and deletion of unstressed syllables.

On the other hand, Roberts et al.(2005), showed that DS children exhibit more phonological delays compared to normal children. For instance, they use a significantly larger number of syllable structure processes than substitution processes. Additionally, the phonological processes used by DS children include cluster reductions, deletion of final

consonants, final nasals, final liquids, palatal fronting, fricative simplification, deaf frication, and lateralization of sibilants.

Summary

Overall, this section discussed various phonological processes. Gammon (1997) addressed the factors influencing phonological development in DS children and provided an overview of the literature on the differences and the processes used by both typical and DS children. Dodd and Leahy (1989) investigated the characteristics of typically developing and DS children, pointing out the similarities and differences between them. Parsons and Iacono (1992) utilized profound methods to examine the speech of DS children, such as the Goldman-Fristoe Test of Articulation, the Parsons and Iacono Test (PIT), and a 5-minute-continued-conversation test, along with naming 35 pictures and 105 pictures. The PIT was used to extract the words which represent the different types of syllables shown in the speech of individuals with delayed language development (i.e., CVC, CV, two syllables, and multi syllables).

These methods will be applied in this research. In addition, many researchers provided an overview of the processes/ errors made during speech production.

Although many discussions and investigations have been conducted regarding the phonological processes of DS children, none of them have examined the phonological processes of Arabic-speaking DS children. Hence, this study investigates the common phonological processes in the speech of Arabic-speaking children with Down Syndrome (DS) in Al-Ramtha city, by comparing their speech to typically-developing children within the same age group.

Chapter Three: Research Methodology

This chapter will discuss the instruments and methods used in this study, also provides participants' information, how they were selected, and describes the data analysis.

3.1 Research Methods

The proposed phonological errors verification consists of three procedures:

The first is Goldman-Fristoe Test of Articulation; second is the Parsons-Iacono Test (PIT), and third is a 5-minute continued- conversational speech. Both the Goldman-Fristoe Test and the PIT were concerned with naming 35 pictures and 105 pictures of different objects, colors, and numbers, respectively.. Goldman-Fristoe Test was used to extract the words which represent the all phonological errors. Also, the PIT was used to extract the words which represent the different types of syllables shown in the speech of individuals with delayed language development (i.e., CVC, CV, two syllables, and multi syllables). In addition, a 5-minute continued conversational speech was used to talk with DS children in 5 minute.

3.2 Data Collection

In order to conduct this research, and to examine the phonological errors of Arabic-speaking DS children including their phonological processes related errors in Al-Ramtha city, in-depth methods were used; PIT, GF and a 5- minute-continued-conversational speech methods.

For the purpose of this study, two groups of children were formed. The first group included 15 Arabic-speaking DS children with ages ranging between five and ten years old. They were selected from the Special Needs Center, AL-Amal Center, and Basmat

Amal center in Al-Ramtha, Irbid Governorate. Those centers provide teaching and learning services to children with DS.

The second group consisted of five typically developed children with no cognitive disorder, learning disability, vision, or hearing defects. This group was chosen randomly with ages ranging between five and eight years old. It is worth noting that the cognitive ages of the DS children are lower than their chronological ages due to a delay in the process of development, so the age range of DS children was intentionally selected to be higher than the age range of normal children, as found by Parsons and Lacono (1992). In order to observe the language performance of DS individuals, three language tests were used including :PIT, GF and a 5- minute-continued-conversational speech methods.

Required data was collected while the children were talking to each other, playing random games, and looking at short stories with pictures; their speech was tape-recorded and transcribed. Further on the three methods mentioned above.

3.3 Data Analysis

Data will be analyzed to detect the presence/absence of the Jordanian Arabic consonants and their correct/incorrect articulation. The presence of a certain phoneme will be confirmed if it is used three times or more, and it will be considered used correctly if it occurs three times or more in its correct context. In addition, the transcribed data will be precisely examined to extract several phonological processes that represent the most frequently occurring errors made, including the final consonant deletion, the use of stops for fricatives, the use of glides for liquids at words initial, stopping, consonant harmony, etc. These errors were analyzed according to the criteria explained in the DEAP-Assessment of Phonology (Dodd et al., 2002).The criteria imply that the errors occurring five or more times in their speech (except for weak syllable deletion) are considered to be

sound pattern errors. However, weak syllables form sound pattern errors when the child deletes them twice or more.

Chapter Four: Results and Discussion

This chapter examines the results and shows the most frequent types of phonological processes errors in DS children in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. The following subsections reveal the main phonological process errors that occur in Arabic-speaking DS children. Subsequently, the findings are discussed in light of the previous studies .

4.1 Overview

The researcher noticed various phonological process errors in the speech of DS children: stridency deletion, lateralization, syllable deletion, initial consonant deletion, fronting, coda deletion, de-emphasis, stopping, backing, final consonant deletion, gliding, Consonant harmony, De- affrication, onset deletion, Metathesis, cluster reduction, glottal replacement, and Nasalization. Moreover, stridency deletion and lateralization were the most frequently presented errors in all Arabic-speaking DS children. Also, differences in phonological processes between both DS males and females were noticed .

It should be mentioned that the study sample included DS children with Fallahi dialect of Jordanian Arabic in Al-Ramtha city, and age groups consisted of 7 females and 8 males.

In this study, the DS children produced different words through three elicitation methods; The Goldman-Fristoe Test of Articulation, the Parsons-Iacono Test (PIT) and through a 5-minute-continued-conversational speech test. Both the Goldman Fristoe Test and the PIT were concerned with naming 35 and 105 pictures, respectively, and a 5-minute-continued-conversational speech.

Table (1) below shows the number of words produced by the DS children through the three elicitation methods and the number of phonological errors.

Table 1: The occurrences of errors and production words in Arabic-speaking children with DS.

	Parsons- Iacono Test (PIT)	Goldman- Fristoe Test (GFT)	5-minute continued conversational speech Test
The number of words	35	105	10
The number of errors	525	1575	150

4.2 Frequency and Types of Phonological Errors That Occur in the Speech of Arabic-Speaking Children with DS.

The frequencies of occurrence of targets used by DS Arabic-Speaking children are presented below:

Figure 1: The frequency of phonological process errors in target words in children with DS.

Figure 4.1 shows that Lateralization and stridency deletion are the most frequent processes in the speech of Arabic-Speaking DS children. Stridency deletion is the deletion of stridency consonant including fricative and affricate such as: /ʃalam /realized as [am]‘flag’ and /dʒubnə/ realized as [ubnə]‘cheese’. According to Dyson and Amayreh (2000), strident consonants are often deleted in the sound of children’s speech. Amayreh and Dyson (1998) showed that the /l/ is the most frequently occurring in Arabic as it is acquired early and rapidly by Jordanian children.

Also, Stoel Gammon (1985) concluded that /l/ is produced as /r/ in Arabic-Speaking DS children. In general, these error patterns were observed in all word positions as shown in figure (4.2) below:

Figure 2: The percentages of the main phonological process errors occurring in DS children.

Figure 4.2 shows that stridency deletion and lateralization which are the most frequent errors in the speech of DS children, followed by syllable deletion the percentage is 13%, initial consonant deletion it is 12%, fronting it is 11%, coda deletion it is 8%, de-emphasis it is 6%, baking and stopping it is 5%, final consonant Deletion it is 3%. In addition, metathesis, gliding, nasalization, cluster reduction, consonant harmony, defrication, onset deletion, and glottal replacement were the least frequent errors that occur in the speech of Arabic-Speaking DS children.

4.3 The Main Phonological Process Errors Occurring in Arabic-Speaking DS Children

The study reveals different phonological process errors in the speech of DS children: fronting, backing, stopping, lateralization, coda deletion, onset deletion, initial

consonant deletion, final consonant deletion, de-emphasis, de-affrication, stridency deletion, syllable deletion, metathesis, gliding, consonants harmony, cluster reduction, glottal replacement, and nasalization .

Below, each error with examples from DS children's speech is presented:

1- Stridency deletion errors: Occurs when the fricatives and affricates sounds are deleted. The total Stridency deletion errors are 499 times. A total number of 456 errors resulted from fricatives deletion errors and 43 errors resulted from affricates deletion errors. The following examples illustrate the most commonly produced errors:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age	Frequency/Percentage
/ʕasʕa:fi:r/	[asʕa:fi:l]	‘birds’	Male-8 years	(456 times/91%)
/ʕalam /	[am]	‘flag’	Male-5 years	
/dʒubnə/	[ubnə]	‘cheese’	Female-7 years	(43 imes/9%)

2- Lateralization errors: Lateralization is defined as when /r/ sound is realized as [l] and /l/ sound is realized as [r] in any position of a word. Children in all age groups produced a total of 499 lateralization errors. The following examples illustrate the most commonly produced errors:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age	Frequency/Percentage
/xja:r /	[hja:l]	‘cucumber’	Female-5 years	(499 times/100%)
/sanju:ra/	[sanu:la]	‘ Siniora’	Male-5 years	
/kursj /	[kulsj]	‘chair’	Male-6 years	
/ruz /	[luz]	‘ rice’	Male-8 years	

3- Weak syllable deletion errors: This error occurs when the unstressed syllable of a word is deleted. In this study this error is repeated 420 times. The most frequently produced weak syllable deletion errors were the following:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/falafil/	[afil]	‘Falafel ’	Female-8 years
/ħali:b/	[bi:b]	‘Milk’	Female-5 years
/tuf-fa:ħa/	[fa:ha]	‘Apple’	Male-7 years

4- Initial consonant deletion: This error takes place when the first consonant in a word is deleted. The most frequently produced error are the following (389 time):

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/mɔz/	[ɔz]	‘banana’	Male-6 years
/ruz/	[uz]	‘ rice’	Female-8 years
/bitza/	[iza]	‘ pizza	’Female-5 years

5- Fronting errors: This error occurs when sounds are normally produced forward from their standard production place. For example, the sound /ʃ/ is realized as [s]. The findings are shown below

Normal Sound	Realized sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/ʃ/	[s]:	/ʃibis/	[sibis]	‘chips’	Female-5years
/k/	[t]:	/ka:s/	[ta:s]	‘cup ’	Female-6years
/g/	[d]:	/galam/	[dalam]	‘ pencil’	Male-9years
/g/	[k]:	/bagara/	[bakala]	‘cow’	Female-7 years
/g/	[t]:	/tʰa:ɡj-jə/	[a:tj-jə]	‘hat ’	Female-6 years
/s/	[θ]:	/bis-sə/	[biθ-θə]	‘cat’	Female-6 years

Children in all age groups produced a total number of 361 fronting errors. The most frequently occurring fronting errors in children with DS were /ʃ/ as [s], /k/ as [t] and /g/ as [d]. For example:

Word	Error	Meaning	Frequency/Percentage
[ʃawarmə]	/sawalmə/	‘Shawarma’	(89times/25%0)
[katʃab]	/tatab/	‘ Ketchup’	(89 times/25%)
[gahwa]	/dahwa/	‘ Coffee’	(74 times/20%)

6 -Coda deletion errors: This error is defined as when the final consonant in a syllable is deleted. Children in all age groups produced a total number of 253 coda deletion errors. The following examples illustrate the most commonly produced errors:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender- Age
/fundʒa:n/	[fuda:n]	‘cup ’	Female-9 years
/wardə /	[wadə]	‘flower’	Male-7 years
/hɪlwa /	[hiwa]	‘sweet’	Male-6 years
/matʰbax /	[mabah]	‘kitchen’	Female-10 years

7 -De-emphasis errors: This error takes place when a loss of the secondary articulation of emphatic consonants is presented, where the sounds /tʰ, dʰ, ðʰ, sʰ/ are realized as [t, d, ð, s]. For example:

Normal sound	Realized sound	Error	Word	Meaning	Gender- Age
/dʰ/	[d]:	/axdʰar/	[ahdal]	‘green’	Male-6 years
/sʰ/	[s]:	/sʰəbə/	[səbə]	‘heater’	Male-10 years

The most commonly produced de-emphasis errors are /sʰ/ as [s] and // as [t] with frequencies of 178 of times. The most frequent errors are the following:

Normal Sound	Realized sound	Error	Word	Meaning	Gender- Age	Frequency/Percentage
/sʰ/	[s]:	/masʰa:sʰa/	[masa:sa]	‘lollipop’	Male-10 years	(56 times/31%)
/tʰ/	[t]:	/tʰa:ɡj-jə/	[ta:tj-jə]	‘hat ’	Female-9 years	(106 times/60%)

8 -Stopping errors: This error is defined as when affricates and fricatives are produced as stops. The most common errors found are summarized below:

Normal sound	Realized sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/dʒ/	[d]:	/ʃadʒwa/	[adwa]	‘dates’	Male-9 years
/s /	[t]:	/siki:nə/	[titi:nə]	‘knife’	Female-8 years
/s /	[d]:	/bis-sə/	[bid-də]	‘cat’	Female-5 years
/tʃ/	[t]:	/tʃaʃitʃ/	[tait]	‘cookie’	Male-10 years

The most frequently occurring stopping errors in DS children were/ s / as [t] and /dʒ/ as [d]. Children in all age groups produced a total of 158 stopping errors as shown in the following example :

Word	Error	Meaning	Frequency/Percentage
/sadʒara/	[sadala]	‘Tree’	(122 times/77%)
/tʃaʃitʃ/	[tait]	‘cookies’	(26 times/16%)

9-Backing errors: It is an error that happens when fronting sounds are made in the back of the mouth. The following examples illustrate the most frequently produced backing errors:

Normal Sound	Realized Sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/x/	[h]:	/mat ^h bax/	[mabah]	‘kitchen’	Male-7 years
/h/	[h]:	/lahmə	[ahmə]	‘meat’	Male-10 years
/θ/	[s]:	/θala:dʒə/	[Sala:də]	‘fridge ’	Female- 9 years
/ð/	[d]:	/iðin/	[idin]	‘ear’	Male- 6 years
/x/	[h]:	/bat ^h i:x/	[bati:h]	‘watermelon’	Male-10years

In general, 148 errors have been found. However, the most frequently occurring backing errors were /x/ as [h] and /ħ/ as [h]. As shown in the following example:

Word	Error	Meaning	Frequency/Percentage
/maxad-də/	[ahad-də]	‘Pillow’	(63 time/42%)
/Xubiz /	[hubiz]	‘Bread’	
/tuf-fa:ħa/	[fa:ha]	‘Apple’	(51 time/34%)
/ħaf-fa:jə/	[haf-fa:jə]	‘Slipper’	

10 -Final consonant deletion errors: This error occurs when the final consonant in the word is deleted. The most frequently produced errors are shown in the following example with a frequency of 105 times:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender/Age
/ʃuba:k/	[uba:]	‘window’	Female-5 years
/ba:b/	[ba:]	‘door’	Female-7 years
/ba:lən/	[ba:lə]	‘balloon’	Male-9 years

11 -Gliding errors: This error is defined as when liquid sounds /l, r/ are realized as glide sounds /j,w/. The most frequently produced gliding errors are shown below:

Normal Sound	Realize d sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender- Age	Frequency/Percentage
/r/	[j]	/ra:s /	[ja:s]	‘head’	Male-8 years	(19 times/%58)
/r/	[j]	/ruz /	[yuz]	‘rice’	Female-9 years	
/l/	[j]	/laħmə /	[yahmə]	‘meat’	Male-6 years	(14 times/%42)
/l/	[j]	/lemu:n/	[yemu:n]	‘lemon’	Female-7 years	

12 -Consonant harmony errors: when the pronunciation of a word is influenced by one of the sounds in that word with frequencies of 26 times, the following examples illustrate the most commonly produced errors:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/hali:b/	[bi:b]	'milk'	Female-5 years
/azrag /	[azaz]	'blue '	Male-5 years

13 -De-affrication errors: This error takes place when affricate sounds are realized as fricatives sounds. Out of total 19 de-affrication errors, 11 errors resulted from de-affrication of /dʒ/and 8 errors resulted from /tʃ/, for example /tʃ/realized as [s]. The most frequent errors are shown in the following example:

Normal Sound	Realized Sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age	Frequency/Percentage
/tʃ/	[s] :	/katʃab/	[tsab]	'ketchup'	Female-9 years	(8 times/42%)
/dʒ /	[z] :	/sidʒa:də/	[iza:zə]	'carpet'	Female-6 years	(11 times/58%)

14-Onset deletion errors: This error is defined as when the first consonant in a syllable is deleted. Children in all age groups produced a total of 19 onset deletion errors. The following examples illustrate the most produced errors:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/burugda:n/	[butuka:n]	'orange '	Male-10 years
/tilfizjøn/	[tizjøn]	'television'	Female-7 years

15 -Metathesis errors: Metathesis happens when consonants place or position is changed in one-word with frequencies of 13 times, the most frequently produced error is the following:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/Dawa:li:/	[dala:wi:]	‘grape leave’	Male-10 years

16 -Cluster reduction errors: When the consonant of the cluster is simplified and omitted this is called a cluster reduction error. This error occurs with frequencies of 12 times. For example:

Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/kta:b /	[ta:b]	‘book’	Male-7 years
/ʃalb /	[sab]	‘dog’	Male-5 years

17 -Glottal replacement errors: This error is defined as when any consonant is realized as a glottal stop [ʔ]. The two consonants that were most commonly produced errors are /ʕ/ and /x/, with frequencies of 6 times; the examples illustrate the most commonly produced errors:

Normal Sound	Realized Sound	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age	Frequency/Percentage
/ʕ/	[ʔ]:	/ʕadʒwa /	[ʔadwa]	‘dates’	Male-10 years	(3 times/%50)
/x/	[ʔ]:	/ xubiz /	[ʔubiz]	‘bread’	Female-8 years	(3 times/%50)

18 -Nasalization errors: the effect on a speech sound when air escapes through the nose, this is called nasalization. In this error /b/ is realized as [m] for example. With frequencies of 2%, the following example illustrate common nasalization error pattern:

Normal Sounds	Realized Sounds	Word	Error	Meaning	Gender-Age
/b/	[m]	/mat ^h bax /	[mamah]	‘kitchen’	girl -5 years

Summary

Almost all common error patterns produced by Arabic-speaking DS children are related to marked and unmarked phonemes. Marked phonemes are sounds that are difficult to obtain early for children, as they are less frequent than unmarked sounds, more complex in articulation and require more cognitive abilities. Interdental sounds like θ and δ are examples of marked phonemes (Broselow, Chen, and Wang, 1998). Arabic-speaking DS children use unmarked sounds such as [h] faster and earlier (Dodd, 1995b). In general, most children with atypical phonological system like DS children, acquire the unmarked, less complex sounds faster and easier (Wang, Chen, Broselow, 1998).

Jakobson (1941) reported that CV syllable shape is a highly frequent pattern, also CV syllable is more unmarked than VC, and children tend to delete unstressed syllables (Kawasaki, 1982). In addition, the coda is unmarked, with a simple articulation, acquired early and more frequently than onset. However, they are difficult in Arabic language. Stoel-Gammon (1988) found that the onset is marked which is harder than the coda, and more accurate in normal children. Wang (1995) showed that voiced stops are more marked than voiceless, hence it is harder to be learned and acquired. Nevertheless, Jakobson (1963) argues that voiceless stops are unmarked, and children start with stop sounds and acquire early.

According to Amayreh and Dyson (1998), the /r/ sound is more difficult and occurs more frequently in Jordanian Arabic. Most Jordanian DS children tend to use [l] as /r/, where [l] sound happened to be unmarked, and easier to acquire. Emphatic sounds are acquired later in DS children. The most frequently occurring de-emphasis errors in DS children were /s^s/ as [s] and /t^s/ as [t], which are unmarked sounds, (Amayreh, 2003). Hence, de-emphasis sounds are acquired before emphasis sounds. According to Amayreh

and Dyson (1998) said that stops, glides and nasals sounds are produced as affricates and fricatives.. In fronting errors, DS children tend to use /s/, /d/ and /t/ since these unmarked sounds are easier to acquire. Stoel-Gammon (1991) reported that English-speaking children acquire /t/ before /k/ because of its unmarked coronal place of articulation and Arabic-speaking children acquire unmarked before marked sounds.

In addition, de-affrication is a complex sound. Children simplify the sounds by producing only one of them and they tend to use single sounds Amayreh (2003). According to Ohala (1999), unlike singletons, consonant clusters are marked and complex sounds; hence, children have difficulty producing them so they tend to delete one of them. Amayreh and Dyson (2000) reported that children acquire cluster errors at the age of 4.

According to Dyson and Paden (1983), children tend to delete initial sounds more than final sounds in Arabic because the final sound in Arabic is more accurate than the initial sound. Smit (2007) states that /d^ʒ/, /q/, /z/, /ʒ/ are acquired later than others sounds . In addition, Jordanian children tend to use stopping, fronting, stridency deletion, and lateralization in their speech. (Ingram et al.,1980).

4.4 .Gender

DS females and males have differences in their speech as shown in figure 4.3; males have more errors than females, more difficulties, and more development delays in their speech. Kumin (2006), Roberts et al. (2005), and Wild et al. (2018). Togram(2015) reported similar results; DS females were more intelligent, more developed, and caught the words faster than DS males. Figure 4.3 and Table (2) below present the descriptive differences in DS males and females with specific numbers in phonological processes in their speech.

Figure 3: The descriptive differences in males and females with DS in phonological processes errors

In addition, table (2) below shows the number of errors in general in females vs males with DS:

Table 2: The numbers of each process in males and females with DS.

	Males	Females
Stridency deletion	275	241
Lateralization	207	210
Syllable deletion	201	180
Initial consonant deletion	199	192
Fronting	183	191
Coda deletion	154	99
Stopping	88	77
Backing	85	78
De-emphasis	72	85
Final consonant deletion	53	49
Consonant harmony	15	8
Onset deletion	13	8

Gliding	11	9
De- affrication	11	10
Glottal replacement	6	3
Metathesis	6	7
Cluster reduction	6	6
Nasalization	1	0

Figure 4.5 below shows the percentages of errors in general in females vs males with DS :

Figure 4: The percentage of phonological errors between males and females.

As seen in figure 4.5, generally, DS females have fewer errors in the phonological system than DS males and are more accurate than males in saying any word or imitating any utterance.

4.5 Discussion

The purpose of this study was to investigate the phonological process errors of 15 Jordanian Arabic- Speaking DS children in Al-Ramtha city, Jordan. The age range for the children groups was between five and ten from the two genders. Moreover, the speech performance of the boys and the girls was compared. The children were observed and

recorded while naming pictures, talking to each other, and playing random games. The speech samples were collected then transcribed and analyzed to observe the presence/absence of the consonants. These errors were analyzed according to the criteria explained in the DEAP- Assessment of phonology (Dodd et al.,2002).

It has been assessed that DS children have a poor ability to produce Arabic consonants, particularly, the consonants involving the back of the mouth such as guttural, laryngeals, uvular fricatives (Waston 2011). Additionally, DS children tended to use stops, nasals and glides over other consonants. Also, in terms of syllable structure, they tended to use CV syllables more. Furthermore, figure 4.5 presents the percentages of the deletion of syllable-final and syllable initial, and figure 4.6 shows the percentage of deletion of word-initial and word-final sounds.

Figure 5: The percentage of the deletion of syllable-final and syllable initial in children with DS.

Figure 6: The percentage of the deletion of word-final and word-initial sounds in children with DS.

Moreover, the findings concluded that the most frequent and difficult process for DS children included lateralization errors, when /r/ sound are realized as [l] in any position in a word, and stridency deletion errors when deleting the fricatives and affricates sounds. Meanwhile, liquids /r/, affricatives, and fricatives were the sounds that were not produced by 90% of the DS children. These findings were in accordance with Amayreh & Dyson (2000) who found that uvularized consonants are the most difficult sounds in Arabic.

In general, DS children made phonological process errors because these processes were influenced by factors that were involved in producing speech. The factors that greatly influenced the phonology system were: cognitive deficits, differences in anatomy, and differences in physiology in DS children. However, Stoel-Gammon (2001) indicated that the factors that affect phonological acquisition in DS children are four; the pre-linguistic stage, the transition to speech, phonology of single words, and phonological characteristics of conversational speech.

From a medical perspective, previous medical studies concluded that DS children make errors in their speech for several physical impairments as shown below :

- Anatomic anomalies and pathophasy. According to Stempfle, Hutten, Fredouille, Brisse&Nessmann,(1999), Ds children suffer from brachycephaly and absence of nasal bone ossification.
- Overall craniofacial anatomy. In general, researchers concluded that DS individuals have reduced airways volume, smaller mid, lower face skeleton, and hard palate. The reduction in upper airway size that caused errors in DS children resulted from the soft tissue with smaller mid, hard palate, and lower face skeleton. (Uong et al. 2001) .
- The vocal tract and laryngeal shape. According to Beck (1997), the differences in the vocal tract setting affect speech production in Ds nerdlilh.
- The tongue and hard palatal shape. DS individuals have an enlarged tongue and a higher palate. (Ardran, Harker&Kemp, 1972)
- An auditory function such as hearing loss, according to Stoel-Gammon (2003), impaired hearing may delete the final consonant in words that are heard .
- Hypotonia, according to (Dodd, Thompson ,2001) DS children have a low muscle tone that affects speech production for DS individuals .
- Anatomical differences. DS individuals have many differences from normal individuals in the oral cavity, also differences in oral musculature effect; small caving, narrow palate, and different oral maculate (Leddy, 1999). Consequently, many sounds are difficult to produce accurately in DS individuals.

The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of Roberts et al. (2005), Van Borsel (1988), Stoel-Gammon (1997;2001), and Parsons &Iacono (1992) which pointed to the same phonological process errors that occur in DS children .

Moreover, the results of the analysis are in line with the results of the studies that have revealed many processes/errors used in DS children's speech including cluster reductions, deletion of final consonants, final nasals, and final liquids, palatal fronting, fricative simplification, de-affrication, and lateralization (Roberts et al.2005).

The findings of this study are consistent with the findings of Stoel-Gammon (1997; 2001), which indicated phonological processes in DS children such as consonant clusters (consonant reduction), final consonant deletion, stopping, gliding, and other processes.

On the one hand, Van Borsel (1988) indicated four common phonological processes among DS children; cluster reduction, deletion of final consonants, fronting of palatals, devoicing of voiced plosives and fricatives. According to Parsons and Iacono (1992), the most frequent phonological processes occurring in DS children are cluster reduction, final consonant deletion, and fronting fricatives.

In an earlier study, Bleile & Schwarz's (1984) findings were in line with this study's findings, which showed that stops, nasals, and glides consonant are easier to produce, while affricates, fricatives, and liquids are sometimes produced with errors.

By contrast, the findings of this study are inconsistent with the findings of Dodd & Leahy (1989) which shows that word production in DS children have the same characteristics of normal children, because DS children have different characteristics than typical children.

The general implications provide a lot of information regarding phonological processes in Arabic language of DS children which are needed to be acknowledged by professors, Dr's, researchers, teachers, and speech therapists for the education process. Likewise, highlighting the difficulties affect the learning process for DS children. These

goals are seen also in previous studies such as Bleile & Schwarz (1984), Van Borsel (1988), Roberts et al. (2005), Stoel-Gammon (1997; 2001), and Parsons and Iacono(1992).

Chapter Five: Summary, Conclusions, and Recommendations

5.1 Introduction

In this chapter, author will represent a summary of the study, the findings that have been concluded, recommendations, and suggestions for this study, also for further research.

5.2 Summary of the Study

To summarize, a study of phonological errors in the speech of Arabic-speaking children with Down Syndrome (DS) in Al-Ramtha city was conducted. It focuses on the phonological processes and processes-related errors.

To achieve the purpose of the study, the speech of two groups of children was examined. The first group consisted of 15 Arabic-speaking DS children, ages between five and ten years. The second group included 5 normal children, aged five to eight years. Data were collected by three procedures: the Goldman-Fristoe Test of Articulation, the Parsons-Iacono Test (PIT) and a 5-minute-continued-conversational speech. These errors were analyzed according to the criteria explained in the DEAP-Assessment of Phonology (Dodd et al., 2002).

This study attempted to achieve the following objectives: first, define the phonological processes errors made by Arabic-speaking DS children. Second, recognize the most frequent phonological errors occurring in Arabic-speaking DS children. Third, compare the phonological performance between normal and DS children.

5.3 Conclusions

First of all, it was noticed that Arabic-speaking DS children in Ramtha city - Jordan had different phonological errors, some errors were frequently occurring in their speech.

Results show that DS children produced different words through three elicitation methods. The most observed that stridency deletion, lateralization, syllable deletion, initial consonant deletion, fronting, coda deletion, de-emphasis, stopping, baking, final consonant deletion, gliding, consonant harmony, de- affrication, onset deletion, metathesis, cluster reduction, glottal replacement, and nasalization. besides, stridency deletion and lateralization were the most frequent error patterns in all DS children.

It is safe to conclude that the phonological processes witnessed in the speech of DS children reflect common natural phonological processes or unmarked processes. The cognitive and physiological deficit DS children suffer from makes it difficult for them to command complex phonological arrangements or articulatory complex gestures.

DS females and males have differences in their speech, generally, DS females have fewer errors in the phonological system than DS males and are more accurate than males in saying any word or imitating any utterance.

5.4 Recommendations

This study's purpose was to investigate the phonological processes errors of the speech of Arabic-speaking children with Down Syndrome (DS) in Al-Ramtha city. Despite the lack of research that investigated the phonological processes in Arabic-speaking DS children, this study suggests that more studies can be conducted in similar contexts such as Autism children and children who suffer from anxiety disorders.

Nonetheless, it is not adequate for this study and its findings to be generalized to all Arabic-speaking DS children in Jordan, and further studies should be conducted in more cities in Jordan such as Irbid, Amman, Salt, and Aqaba. Furthermore, this study is based only on the phonological processes in Arabic-speaking DS children; more and further studies should be conducted in other fields such as morphology, syntax, pragmatics, and semantics .

It is hoped that this study will attract and motivate more researchers in the studies related to phonological processes in order to expand further results in Jordanian DS children in the future. It is recommended that upcoming studies on the phonological process's domain involve the phonetics field to enhance the generalizability of the findings.

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التحليل الصوتي لأخطاء الأطفال الذين يعانون من متلازمة داون عند الكلام الناطقين باللغة العربية في مدينة الرمثا، الأردن.

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الملخص

تهدف هذه الدراسة إلى البحث في العمليات الصوتية للأطفال الناطقين باللغة العربية المصابين بمتلازمة داون في مدينة الرمثا-الأردن، وتتضمن العمليات الصوتية والأخطاء المتعلقة بالعمليات الصوتية. للإجابة على هذا السؤال، قمنا بمقارنة مجموعتين من الاطفال من السكان الأردنيين في مدينة الرمثا الناطقين باللغة العربية، تضمنت المجموعة الأولى 15 طفلاً من متلازمة داون يتحدثون العربية، أما المجموعة الثانية قد تضمنت 5 أطفال غير مصابين بمتلازمة داون، تراوحت أعمار الأطفال بين 5 إلى 10 سنوات في المجموعتين، وقد تم استخدام ثلاثة طرق لإنتاج الكلام، اختبار بارسونس و ايكونو، اختبار جولدمانفريستوا واختبار التحدث خلال 5 دقائق، تم جمع العينات من خلال التسجيل الصوتي للأطفال، نسخ النص منه ومن ثم تحليل هذه الأخطاء من خلال علم تقييم الأصوات لدود عام 2000 أظهرت النتائج أخطاء العمليات الصوتية التي تحدث في اللغة العربية لدى اطفال متلازمة داون، كما قد تم العثور على أكثر أنواع الاخطاء الصوتية حدوثاً وبشكل متكرر في حديث لاطفال الناطقين بالعربية الذين يعانون من متلازمة داون.

الكلمات المفتاحية: العمليات الصوتية، أطفال متلازمة داون، الأطفال الناطقين باللغة العربية، الأخطاء